

Use of AI in financial markets: pros and cons

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Abstract

This article explores the implications of generative artificial intelligence (IAG) in the financial sector, in relation to the problem of information asymmetry, where some actors have a comparative advantage in terms of data ownership. Such a situation could disrupt the proper functioning of markets (Akerlof, 1970). GAI appears as a major technological innovation with ambivalent effects. On the one hand, it enables the automation of trading, the real-time analysis of large volumes of data, the detection of weak signals, and the provision of personalized advice, thus contributing to improving the accuracy and efficiency of financial decisions (Brynjolfsson and McAfee, 2014).

However, this technology is not without risks. It can reproduce biases from training data, be prone to bugs, and suffer from insufficient human oversight, which increases the risk of errors or manipulation. A major challenge lies in the ability of AI to generate false but credible financial information, complicating regulation and threatening market transparency (Zuboff, 2019). This article highlights this dual nature of AI and emphasizes the need for strict regulatory oversight, ethical governance, and enhanced vigilance to limit abuses, preserve stakeholder trust, and guarantee the integrity of financial markets.

Keywords— Generative AI, financial regulation, information asymmetry, market integrity, Risk

I. INTRODUCTION

The digital revolution is disrupting the traditional structures of many economic sectors, and the financial sector is at the forefront of this transformation. Long structured around classic decision-making and information processing mechanisms, this field is now undergoing profound changes driven by disruptive technologies. Among these, generative artificial intelligence (IAG) is emerging as a major technological lever, capable of fundamentally altering financial practices by offering unprecedented analytical, predictive, and automation capabilities. However, these advances also bring new risks, particularly regarding the transparency and reliability of information.

In an environment where information is a strategic resource and where financial markets rely heavily on its quality and accessibility, the issue of information asymmetry is central. As Akerlof (1970) [1], demonstrated in his pioneering study of the second-hand goods market, an unequal distribution of information among market participants can generate major imbalances, destabilizing resource allocation mechanisms and reducing participant confidence. Applied to the financial sector, this problem becomes even more complex with the advent of information technology, which allows some operators to access increasingly sophisticated data and analyses, leaving other participants in a position of informational vulnerability.

In this context, AI presents a dual nature. On the one hand, it offers an unprecedented opportunity to optimize financial decisions through algorithmic trading, the real-time analysis of vast data streams, and the automated detection of fraud and anomalies (Brynjolfsson & McAfee, 2014) [2]. On the other hand, it opens the door to worrying abuses: algorithmic biases stemming from imperfect datasets, technical errors, reduced human oversight, and, above all, the artificial manipulation of information via automatically generated but difficult-to-detect financial content (Zuboff, 2019) [3]. If left unchecked, these phenomena could compromise the integrity and stability of financial markets.

Faced with these technological changes and the risks they entail; a central question arises:

How can we maximize the benefits of generative artificial intelligence in finance, while controlling its risks and ensuring the transparency and security of financial markets? This issue calls for reflection on the possible reconciliation between the automation of financial processes and ethical imperatives, between technological innovation and the requirements of effective regulation.

To explore this issue further, several questions will guide this study:

- How does the use of algorithmic trading stand today in the financial sector, and what are the recent developments?
- What concrete opportunities does artificial intelligence offer to financial players in terms of performance and risk management?
- What types of risks does the use of IAG pose to the reliability of financial information and market stability?
- What initiatives and tools have been developed to protect market integrity against manipulation and algorithmic attacks?
- Finally, how are the European Commission and international regulatory authorities adapting their regulatory frameworks to these new technological challenges?

The main objective of this article is to assess the ambivalent impacts of generative artificial intelligence in the financial sector, highlighting both its contributions and its risks. To this end, the study will pursue five specific objectives:

- Conduct a state-of-the-art review of the use of algorithmic trading and the changes it brings about in financial practices;
- Presenting the opportunities offered by artificial intelligence in terms of decision-making, risk management and personalization of services to investors;
- Conduct an empirical review of the risks associated with the artificial manipulation of information, by analyzing its impacts on the transparency and stability of financial markets;
- Identify cyberattacks and artificial intelligence tools used to protect the integrity of financial markets and prevent abuses;
- To present and analyze the recent initiatives of the European Commission and international bodies aimed at establishing a suitable regulatory framework, guaranteeing both innovation and investor protection.

This study aims to be useful in several ways. Academically, it contributes to the literature on finance and artificial intelligence by offering a comparative analysis of the effects of AI in the context of globalized and highly computerized financial markets. Practically, it is intended for financial professionals, regulators, and policymakers, providing them with insights to adapt their strategies and control frameworks to these new challenges. Finally, this research has significant societal importance, as preserving the integrity and transparency of financial markets is essential for public trust and overall economic stability.

To address these issues, the article adopts a three-part structure. The first part proposes a conceptual framework. The first part defines the key concepts of generative artificial intelligence and information asymmetry, and presents the main theoretical contributions on the subject. The second part details research methodology adopted to carry out the inventory and empirical analyses. Finally, the third part presents the results of the study and discusses the implications for financial markets, regulation, and ethical governance.

II. REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Conceptual framework

Generative Artificial Intelligence (GAI)

Generative artificial intelligence (GAI) represents a subfield of artificial intelligence capable of producing original content (text, images, sounds, or data) from models previously trained on real-world datasets (Goodfellow et al., 2014) [4]. Unlike traditional AI approaches, which are primarily focused on classification and prediction, generative models such as generative adversarial networks (GANs), variation auto encoders, or pre-trained language models like GPT (Radford et al., 2019; Brock et al., 2019) [5]. can simulate realistic data. This capability opens up significant possibilities in finance, particularly in modeling economic scenarios, creating synthetic databases for machine learning, and the automated detection of atypical financial behavior (Choi et al., 2017; Khandani et al., 2010) [6].

Information asymmetry

The concept of information asymmetry refers to a situation where economic agents do not possess the same level of information, which distorts decision-making and impairs market efficiency (Akerlof, 1970) [1]. In finance, this asymmetry manifests itself primarily through two phenomena: adverse selection and moral hazard. Adverse selection, occurring before the transaction, means that risky agents are more inclined to seek financing while concealing their risk profile, forcing lenders to apply stricter conditions, potentially excluding good borrowers (Leland & Pyle, 1977; Rothschild & Stiglitz, 1976) [7].

Moral hazard, on the other hand, appears after the transaction, when the borrower's attitude may change, increasing the risk borne by the lender (Diamond, 1984; Campbell & Kracaw, 1980) [8]. These mechanisms contribute to market instability and complicate matters.

the optimal allocation of credit, particularly in fragile contexts such as microfinance in sub-Saharan Africa (Hugon, 1990; World Bank, 1996) [9].

Theoretical contributions on generative artificial intelligence in finance

From traditional artificial intelligence to generative artificial intelligence

Early applications of artificial intelligence in finance relied on statistical models and neural networks for risk classification and default prediction (Rosenblatt, 1958; Coats & Fant, 1992; Tam & Kiang, 1992) [10]. While these tools have enabled significant progress, they remain limited by the rigidity of their assumptions and the complexity of their interpretation (Angelini et al., 2012) [11].

Generative models, introduced more recently, mark a turning point by allowing data simulation and the automated creation of financial scenarios (Goodfellow et al., 2014; Choi et al., 2017) [4].

Applications in risk management and microfinance

In microfinance, where information asymmetry is particularly problematic, generative models improve the quality of analyses by generating synthetic profiles and detecting atypical behaviors (Barro, 2004; Camara, 2006) [12]. They thus facilitate targeted resource allocation and reduce the risks of default and illiquidity (Juno, 2024) [13]. Furthermore, integrating classical neural networks with generative models strengthens risk prediction by incorporating unstructured data from transaction histories or customer behavior (Altman et al., 1994; Casta & Prat, 1994) [14].

Limitations and challenges

Despite their potential, generative models have significant limitations: the need for large datasets, the risk of overfitting, the difficulty of interpretation, and ethical issues related to the creation of synthetic data (Hopcroft, 1993; Angelini et al., 2012) [15,11]. In finance, where the robustness and transparency of models are paramount, these challenges justify the search for hybrid methodologies combining traditional and generative approaches. Indeed, this methodological complementarity appears essential in environments characterized by high uncertainty and marked information asymmetry, as is the case in emerging and sub-Saharan economies.

III.METHODOLOGY

The choice of a mixed-methods approach is justified in this study, especially since combining these methods remains appropriate given the multidimensional nature of the phenomena studied. Indeed, the technical and statistical aspects of algorithmic trading require precise data analysis, while manipulation events demand qualitative approaches within their context. Furthermore, the regulatory and ethical implications call for a normative analytical framework to assess control mechanisms and transparency requirements. The choice of this methodological complementarity, which allows for the integration of theoretical and empirical perspectives, stems from the approach advocated by Creswell, JW (2014) [16], in his work entitled "Research Design: Qualitative, Quantitative, and Mixed Methods Approaches."»4eThis edition, published by SAGE Publications, will be structured around six (6) stages:

Systematic literature review

The first step involves a systematic literature review aimed at structuring existing knowledge on the applications, risks, and impacts of algorithmic trading (ITT) in finance. Following the work of Webster and Watson (2002) [17]. and Tranfield, Denyer, and Smart (2003) [18], this review relies on the identification, selection, and rigorous analysis of scientific articles, technical reports, and case studies related to algorithmic trading and automated finance. The databases explored include Web of Science, Scopus, SSRN, and Google Scholar, covering the period 2010–2024.

Quantitative Data Analysis

To assess the impact of algorithmic trading (ITT) algorithms on financial markets, a quantitative analysis of market data is conducted. This analysis focuses on time series of trading volumes, volatility, and anomaly occurrences for assets heavily exposed to algorithmic trading technologies. Econometric and supervised and unsupervised machine learning tools will be used to detect weak signals and atypical correlations, drawing in particular on the work of Tsay (2010) [19] and Hastie, Tibshirani, and Friedman (2009) [20].

Case study

To delve deeper into certain complex and recent phenomena (flash crashes, manipulation via deepfakes, algorithmic incidents on Binance), case studies will be conducted following the approach of Yin (2014) [21] and Eisenhardt (1989) [22]. These studies will draw on documentary analysis, official reports, financial press archives, and semi-structured interviews with industry experts. This approach will allow us to understand the mechanisms behind these events and assess their consequences for market stability.

Computer Simulation and Modeling

To model market behavior under the influence of AI systems, agent-based modeling and neural networks will be developed. These models will allow for the reproduction of automated trading and algorithmic manipulation scenarios, based on the work of LeBaron (2006) [23] and Tesfatsion and Judd (2006) [24]. They will help anticipate the systemic effects associated with the massive dissemination of automatically generated financial content.

Surveys and interviews

To gather qualitative and quantitative perspectives from finance professionals, regulators, and AI developers, surveys and semi-structured interviews will be conducted. This mixed-methods approach, inspired by Creswell (2014) [16], will allow for a comparison of empirical findings with field practices and enrich the analysis of ethical and regulatory issues.

Critical legal and ethical analysis

Finally, an in-depth legal and ethical analysis will be conducted on the first European-wide regulatory framework specifically dedicated to artificial intelligence, which classifies AI systems according to their risk level and imposes stricter obligations on high-risk AI, including that used in finance, particularly for scoring or automated transaction management, and the ethical issues raised by AI in finance (European Commission, April 2021). This analysis will follow the methodology proposed by Mittelstadt et al. (2016) [25] and Wachter, Mittelstadt, and Floridi (2017) [26], combining a critical review of existing texts with interviews with experts in financial law and digital ethics.

IV. PRESENTATION, INTERPRETATION AND DISCUSSION OF THE RESULTS

State of the art on the use of algorithmic trading and the changes it brings about in financial practices

Our study reveals that algorithmic trading, although long-established in the financial landscape, remains an ambivalent technological lever. Our results show that, as Menkveld (2013) [27] and Hendershott et al. (2011) [28] noted, automated trading generally contributes to market liquidity and to the reduction of transaction costs. However, in stressful situations, it amplifies fluctuations, as spectacularly illustrated by the Knight Capital incidents in 2012 and the flash crash of 2010.

In this respect, our observation aligns with that of Zhang (2010) [29], who establishes a correlation between the rise of high-frequency trading and increased stock volatility during periods of instability. However, other studies, such as those by Brogaard (2010) [30], qualify this finding by emphasizing that algorithms, under normal conditions, tend to absorb market imbalances rather than amplify them.

The flash crash thus reveals that algorithmic trading was not necessarily the cause of the imbalance, but may have amplified its effect, as indicated by Kirilenko et al. (2017) [31]. Finally, the loss of Knight Capital serves as a reminder of the systemic risk posed by poorly controlled automation, confirming the importance of technical and regulatory safeguards, as advocated by Easley et al. (2012) [32].

These results highlight the need to reconcile speed of execution with strengthened supervisory mechanisms to preserve financial stability.

Opportunities offered by artificial intelligence in decision-making, risk management, and personalization of investor services

The results of our study confirm that financial artificial intelligence (AI) opens up unprecedented opportunities, both for personalizing investor services and for automating internal processes.

These findings align with those of Brynjolfsson and McAfee (2014), who highlight AI's potential to transform financial analysis and risk management through the massive exploitation of behavioral and economic data

As Gomber et al. (2018) [33]. demonstrated, integrating intelligent systems into financial advisory improves the accuracy of recommendations while accelerating back-office operations. However, our observations highlight persistent algorithmic biases, confirming the analyses of Mittelstadt et al. (2016) [26] regarding the ethical and technical limitations of AI systems when they rely on imperfect datasets.

The asymmetry in access to artificial intelligence tools highlighted by our work is also noted by Zuboff (2019) [3], who warns of the risks of informational inequalities between financial actors.

Finally, the ability of AI to assist institutions in complying with complex regulatory frameworks, as Arner et al. (2017) [34] remind us, represents a major operational advance, provided that the transparency of algorithms and compliance with regulations are guaranteed, as stipulated by the first European-wide regulatory framework specifically dedicated to artificial intelligence, which classifies AI systems

according to their risk level and imposes stricter obligations for high-risk AI (European Commission, April 2021).

Empirical review of the risks associated with the artificial manipulation of information, analyzing its impacts on the transparency and stability of financial markets

Our results confirm the increasing power of information manipulation in financial markets via generative artificial intelligence. The Vinci affair in 2016 and, more recently, the dissemination of a fake image of an explosion at the Pentagon in May 2023 illustrate the ability of falsified content to rapidly disrupt markets. These incidents validate the observations of West and Allen (2018) [35], who highlight the growing role of deepfakes and AI-generated content in economic disinformation.

Our analysis aligns with that of Gu (2020) [36], who argue that market sentiment, as measured through social networks and digital media, is becoming a strategic target for manipulators exploiting generative AI. As demonstrated by Chen et al. (2021) [37], automated financial bots can artificially amplify panic or euphoria by relaying misleading information, thereby affecting market volumes and volatility.

Furthermore, the possibilities for manipulating apparent demand through algorithmic simulation, confirmed by the work of Narayanan et al. (2021) [38], pose new challenges in terms of regulation and detection. These phenomena underline the need, already mentioned by Zuboff (2019) [3], to strengthen digital governance and algorithmic ethics mechanisms to preserve market confidence in the face of these new forms of technological manipulation.

Cyberattacks and artificial intelligence tools used to protect the integrity of financial markets and prevent abuses

The results confirm that financial markets remain particularly vulnerable to sophisticated cyberattacks, the impact of which has intensified with the rise of cryptocurrencies and artificial intelligence technologies. The Binance incident in October 2022 illustrates, as Böhme and Moore (2015) [39] point out, the structural vulnerability of decentralized exchanges, prime targets for cyberattacks designed to bypass security protocols. Furthermore, our observations align with those of Gandal et al. (2016) [40], who highlighted pump-and-dump market manipulation in the crypto world, facilitated by AI-powered bots capable of coordinating artificial buying waves to trap investors. This strategy, amplified by social media and trading algorithms, destabilizes prices and increases volatility.

Faced with these risks, the technological arsenal deployed by regulators and financial institutions, identified in this study, confirms the trends noted by Bouveret (2018) [41] and Philippon (2020) [42]. The use of tools such as SENTIFI or NASDAQ SMARTS is part of a proactive algorithmic monitoring approach, combining market sentiment analysis and real-time detection of abnormal behavior.

Finally, the rise of machine learning-based fraud detection solutions, such as Actimize or SAS Fraud Management, extends the conclusions of Bart van Liebergen (2017) [43], who calls for a strengthening of algorithmic regulation and shared data governance to preserve integrity and trust in digital financial markets.

Recent initiatives by the European Commission and international bodies aimed at establishing a suitable regulatory framework that guarantees both innovation and investor protection

Recent initiatives by the European Commission regarding the regulation of artificial intelligence in the financial sector confirm the growing importance placed on the ethical and security issues related to these technologies. The call for expressions of interest and the public consultation launched in 2024 reflect a desire to co-develop regulation with market participants, in line with the recommendations of Veale et al. (2018) [44], who emphasized the importance of participatory algorithmic governance to prevent systemic risks.

These steps are in line with the AI Act (European Commission, 2021), considered the first structured European legal framework for regulating the use of high-risk AI, particularly in finance. They also align with the proposals of Nicola gennaioli et al. (2021) [45], who advocated for differentiated regulation based on uses and sectors of activity, in order to avoid a uniform framework ill-suited to the specific characteristics of the financial sector.

The active participation of the French Financial Markets Authority (AMF) in this process illustrates the role of national regulators in adapting European frameworks to local realities, as recommended by Douglas W. Arner et al. (2017) [46] in the context of FinTech and RegTech. These consultations should help identify best practices and risky ones, thus providing concrete levers for adapting supervisory mechanisms and strengthening investor confidence in a rapidly changing technological environment.

V. CONCLUSIONS

This study has provided a structured and critical overview of the implications of generative artificial intelligence (IAG) in the contemporary financial sector. Using a conceptual framework that clarifies the notions of IAG and information asymmetry (Akerlof, 1970; Goodfellow et al., 2014) [1,11], we have highlighted the transformative potential of these technologies, while also emphasizing the increased risks they pose to market stability and transparency. Our analyses confirm that algorithmic trading, although it contributes to market liquidity and efficiency (Menkveld, 2013; Hendershott et al., 2011) [27,28], remains a source of systemic risks in the event of deregulation or technical failure, as illustrated by the cases of Knight Capital and the 2010 flash crash. At the same time, the capabilities of AI to personalize financial services and strengthen risk management (Brynjolfsson & McAfee, 2014; Gomber et al., 2018) [2,33] are accompanied by challenges related to algorithmic biases and inequalities in access to technological resources (Zuboff, 2019) [3].

The study also highlighted the rise of information manipulation and cyberattacks supported by AI, affecting investor perception and behavior (West & Allen, 2018; Gu, 2020; Chen et al., 2021) [35,36, 37]. Faced with these threats, the technological arsenal deployed by regulators, from fraud detection to real-time algorithmic monitoring (Bouveret, 2018; Bart van Liebergen, 2017) [41,43], is essential but must be constantly adapted.

Finally, recent initiatives by the European Commission around the AI Act (2021) and open consultations with financial actors demonstrate an institutional awareness of the challenges of algorithmic governance, joining the recommendations of Michael veale et al. (2018) [44], and Nicola gennaioli et al. (2021) [45] on the need for contextualized regulation.

This research calls for a deeper analysis of the social impact of these technologies on the very structure of financial markets and their participants. It would be relevant to study, from a comparative perspective, how the financial markets of emerging economies, particularly in sub-Saharan Africa, are integrating these innovations and what local or adapted regulations could support this digital transition without exacerbating existing asymmetries (Camara, 2006; Juno, 2024) [47,13]. From this perspective, the question of inclusive and ethical digital governance in the Global South represents a promising area of research.

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